

FORMATION OF THE NATIONAL STATE ADMINISTRATION SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN DURING THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE

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Abstract: In the years of independence, the legal basis for elections to local representative bodies was also improved. All necessary conditions have been created for the high-level election of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. During the years of independence, there were significant positive changes in the structure of the republic's gross domestic product.

Key words: Republic, Independence, constitution, principle, United Nations, High Council, presidency, Law, election, Oliy Majlis, deputy.

After the independence of Uzbekistan, a radical change occurred in the constitutional history of our country. It was an objective necessity arising from the demand of the times. This need became a reality at the end of 1992.

The main purpose of the Constitution is the principle of serving human interests. That is why its section after "Basic Principles" is directly devoted to human rights and freedoms and duties. In the following places, a special place is given to the building principles of society and individual and state power.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. After Uzbekistan gained state independence, a modern and effective form of state administration - the presidential system - began to be established in the country. In the development of world statehood, there are mainly two forms of government - monarchical and republican forms. The republic, in turn, has the forms of a parliamentary republic and a presidential republic. The presidential republic is the most common form of government today.

The position of President in Uzbekistan was established on March 24, 1990 at the first session of the Supreme Council. On December 29, 1991, the referendum of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the election of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan were held on the issue of the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Law "On the Election of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan" adopted on November 18, 1991 and the general election held on its basis gained great importance in strengthening the presidential power in Uzbekistan. During the years of independence, the institution of the presidency was fully formed. We will try to prove this idea below.

During the years of independence, the legal basis for elections to local representative bodies was also improved. Article 1 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Elections of People's Deputies to Regional, District and City Councils" (May 5, 1994) defines the basic principles of holding elections to local representative bodies in Uzbekistan at the level of democratic values. "Elections to regional, district and city Councils of People's Deputies will be held for a period of five years on the basis of multi-party constituencies. Deputies of regional, district and city councils of people's deputies are elected by secret ballot on the basis of universal, equal and direct suffrage.

Elections to the Parliament of Uzbekistan based on democratic principles were held for the first time on December 25, 1994. The first election to the Oliy Majlis during the period of independence was a practical expression of the democratic processes that are increasingly developing in the country. Citizens' rights were appreciated in all aspects in the elections held on the basis of multi-party and alternative.

As a result of organizational and mass work on preparation for the election based on democratic values, which took place on December 5, 1999, 250 regional electoral districts and 7,723 polling stations were established in the country. More than 100,000 responsible activists worked in district and precinct election commissions. A list of more than 12.5 million citizens with the right to vote has been drawn up. More than 1,200 candidates were nominated for Oliy Majlis deputies, and an average of 5-7 candidates competed for each seat. During the election campaign, 250 Oliy Majlis deputies were elected.

Elections to regional, district and city Councils of People's Deputies held on December 5, 1999 were also held on the basis of democratic principles. In these elections, the legal basis for nominating candidates for deputies from 5 political parties, representative authorities, voter initiative groups was established, and various social strata and groups fought for their representatives to be elected as deputies.

The presidential elections held in our country on January 9, 2000 and December 23, 2007 were also held on the basis of democratic principles - multi-party and alternative. Candidates' election campaigns were conducted on the basis of transparency and equal rights. All necessary conditions have been created for the high-level election of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The nomination of presidential candidates by the political parties and voter initiative groups in the country, the debates between the candidates in the pre-election campaign, and the processes of conducting the elections took place on

the basis of democratic principles, these processes were recognized by international experts.

During the years of independence, there were significant positive changes in the structure of the republic's gross domestic product. For example, in 2010, compared to 2000, the share of industry in the composition of the gross domestic product increased by 1.7 times, the share of the agricultural sector by 1.8 times, the share of transport and communication networks by 1.5 times, and the share of the service sector by 1, increased by 3 times. As a result, 24% of the gross domestic product is contributed by industry, 17.5% by agriculture, 7% by construction, 7.7% by transport, 12.4% by the communication sector, and by services, this figure is from 37% to 49%. Came.

In addition, fundamental improvement of the system of payment of wages, pensions, allowances and scholarships, unconditional protection of the rights and legal interests of pensioners, students and other socially needy strata of the population, the goods they buy in all regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan and in order to create favorable conditions for making payments for services without obstacles, the order of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 2, 2017 "Additional measures to improve the mechanism of payment of wages, pensions, allowances and scholarships" Decision No. PQ-2753 was adopted.

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